

5G Private Networks for Rural Communities: Use Cases and Field Trials

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Abstract—Providing high-speed and reliable wireless connectivity can be challenging in rural areas. 5G private networks can be utilized to provide wireless connectivity in these areas to enhance business-critical applications for different types of industries, small-medium enterprises, agriculture, government entities, etc. This paper presents results of the Horizon Europe COMMECT project regarding 5G private network deployments in rural areas. Specifically, use cases that can be enabled in rural and remote areas by deploying 5G private networks are presented, and typical challenges of 5G private network deployments are addressed. Moreover, two selected use cases, namely, a forestry industry use case and a livestock transportation use case, are detailed with a focus on connectivity requirements, possible network deployment strategies, and initial insights from their respective field trials. This paper provides one of the first contributions related to the deployment of 5G private networks in rural areas.

Index Terms—5G private networks, 5G public networks, field trials, forestry, livestock transportation, rural areas, use cases.

I. INTRODUCTION

Fifth Generation (5G) networks are designed to handle a massive number of connected devices, support high data rates, and provide ultra-low latency, which enables support of various demanding applications [1]. Similarly to older generations of mobile networks (4G/3G), Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) provide services over the so-called *5G public network* to individual users and businesses on a subscription basis. Public 5G networks are typically managed and maintained by the MNOs and are primarily designed for mobile broadband services such as voice calls, access to the Internet, gaming, and video streaming, over large nationwide areas.

5G private networks, or Non-Public Networks (NPNs) following the Third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) terminology, are localized networks dedicated to specific organizations and enterprises, and they are built and managed by the organization or a third-party provider, e.g. an MNO, on their behalf [2]. Typically, private networks allow access only to a limited set of devices (e.g. devices from employees and IoT devices for the enterprise) in a limited area (or number of areas). Further, private networks are customized so that priority or enhanced quality is given to the limited set of services that are crucial for the business or the enterprise. Additionally, due

to data sensitivity and security reasons, private networks can be organized to keep communication data and/or operations and management data within the enterprise premises. The focus of these 5G private networks has been on industries that demand high reliability, low latency, and secure connectivity, such as manufacturing, logistics, healthcare, and transportation [3] in urban and suburban areas, while their deployment applicability in rural areas remains not sufficiently addressed.

Connectivity in rural areas is challenging for traditional MNOs due to investments in building public 5G network infrastructure for scarcely populated areas [4], resulting in large distances between base stations and low investment in capacity per base station. This results in lower quality or unreliable Internet access, affecting residents, businesses, and essential services, which hampers economic development and quality of life for rural communities. 5G private networks could potentially bridge the digital divide between urban and rural areas by offering access to 5G, even in the most remote and isolated areas. In fact, 5G private networks can be customized to the specific needs of the local communities and enable use cases that were otherwise infeasible.

The Horizon Europe COMMECT project [5] is investigating how to enhance connectivity in rural areas by addressing the applicability of 5G private networks and performing initial field tests of the envisaged deployments, which is the motivation for this study. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents potential use cases in rural areas and the associated challenges. Section III describes two COMMECT use cases enabled with 5G private networks, namely a forestry use case and a livestock transportation use case. Section IV discusses the COMMECT's initial network design considerations and field tests for the two selected use cases. Finally, Section V concludes the paper.

II. USE CASES AND CHALLENGES FOR 5G PRIVATE NETWORKS IN RURAL AREAS

The modular design of 5G systems, as well as the trend of network functions virtualization, have enabled two main categories of 5G private networks [6] [7] [8].

Standalone 5G private networks. This deployment category, also denoted as Standalone Non-Public Networks (SNPN) by 3GPP, does not use any network function from a

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Public Land Mobile Network (PLMN) operated by the public MNO i.e., all of the network components deployed are at the enterprise premises.

Hybrid 5G private networks. This deployment category, also denoted as Public Network Integrated NPN (PNI-NPN) by 3GPP, means that the 5G private network uses functions from one or more PLMNs. For example, in one option, the user data of the 5G private network remains within the enterprise, whereas (part of) the Radio Access Network (RAN) and control functions are shared with the PLMN. In another option, which is a special case also known as “Virtual 5G Private Networks”, the private network is fully dependent on the PLMN by utilizing both the RAN and core of the PLMN via a virtual network slice [7].

Hereafter we present potential use cases in rural areas that can be enabled with the deployment of 5G private networks. Moreover, an overview of the related deployment challenges is also provided.

A. Potential Use Case Enablement in Rural Areas

The deployment of 5G private networks in rural areas could enable residents and local enterprises to experience faster download and upload speeds, facilitating more efficient access to online services, such as e.g. video streaming. Moreover, reduced latency could enable real-time applications like video conferencing, which, combined with high-speed Internet, will enable remote working and telecommuting, thereby boosting the local economy and contributing to population growth.

5G private networks can enable precision agriculture and smart farming applications. For example, drones equipped with cameras could upload high-definition videos and images to be used for crop monitoring and analysis of invasive weeds [9]. Remote maintenance and diagnosis of agricultural machines in the farm fields could also be supported [4].

Mines are also typically located in remote areas and can benefit from 5G private networks, which offer reliable communications and enable safer operations by, e.g. sensing early disaster signals [2]. Moreover, 5G private networks can improve maritime communications by, e.g. enabling the communication between offshore platforms and onshore facilities [4].

Healthcare and public safety are also sectors that would benefit from 5G private networks. Specifically, remote healthcare can be supported by providing infrastructure for medical assistance, e.g. remote surgery [4]. Public safety will also be improved by monitoring the environment and critical infrastructure, e.g., bridges and power lines. Then, early prediction of failures and disasters could be facilitated. Similarly, rescue missions in remote areas could be more easily performed.

The selected COMECT use cases where 5G private networks are considered viable connectivity solutions are livestock transportation and forestry, which are explained in more detail in Section III.

B. Challenges for 5G Private Deployment in Rural Areas

Currently, two important frequency bands are considered for 5G private networks, namely 3.3 – 4.2 GHz (band n77)

and 24.25 – 27.50 GHz (band n258). The spectrum regulations should allow for simplified license acquisition, licensing rules, and license verification procedures for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) to make them far less demanding and complex than licensing rules for MNOs. Moreover, customized pricing can be considered for rural areas, depending on the local area covered and the potential number of users served by the 5G private network. As spectrum license conditions for MNOs also allow for sub-leasing (part) of their licensed spectrum, enterprises can either acquire separate local licensed spectrum from the regulator or ‘sub-lease it’ from the MNOs.

The choice of bandwidth size for the private 5G frequency license is also challenging as the regulators allow for different bandwidth sizes in a multiple of 10 MHz [10]. To address the upcoming demand, most 5G private network deployments aim at local spectrum licenses of at least 50 MHz. Moreover, the license conditions include Time Division Duplex (TDD) frame configuration requirements. The regulators require that 5G private networks operating in the same or neighbouring TDD frequency bands as PLMNs use TDD schemes that are synchronized to and use the same uplink to downlink TDD frame ratio as the PLMNs. This could restrict the performance of 5G private networks as some applications in rural areas require higher uplink than downlink speeds [9].

There are also challenges related to infrastructure deployment and operation costs. Depending on the 5G private network deployment (e.g. SNPN or NPI-NPN), there is a different Total Cost of Ownership (TCO) and scaling/customization dependency on the MNOs, ranging from high TCO and low scaling/customization dependency on PLMNs for the fully independent SNPNs to low TCO and high scaling/customization dependency on the PLMN for the virtually sliced PNI-NPNs. Investment in building and operating network infrastructure can be costly, and business models are needed to make these networks economically viable in rural areas.

Finally, the availability of transport networks connecting the local 5G private network to the Internet is also challenging in rural areas. Here, Fixed Wireless Access (FWA) could be an alternative, especially in scenarios where laying physical cables is impractical or too costly for the ‘list-mile access’. Additionally, satellite communications are also an alternative to provide backhauling in remote areas where terrestrial network infrastructure is limited or non-existent. Even though modern satellite communications are closing the gap to terrestrial broadband services, further developments are necessary to support ultra-low latency and high throughput.

III. 5G PRIVATE NETWORKS FOR FORESTS AND LIVESTOCK TRANSPORTATION

The Horizon Europe COMECT project explores possibilities for deploying 5G private networks to support the forestry and livestock transportation sectors, in Norway and Denmark, respectively. Hereafter, we describe the use cases and specific applications.

Fig. 1. 5G Private Networks (a) on wheels for forestry and (b) at the remote farm for livestock transportation.

A. Forestry Use Cases

Norway's forests, covering approximately 33% of the land area, play a significant role in the country's economy and environmental stewardship. Sustainable forest management practices are integral to Norway's approach, ensuring the long-term health of the forests while supporting a range of economic activities. Norway's forestry sector faces a notable challenge in terms of digitization. The industry's value chain has yet to fully leverage technological advancements, particularly in terms of connectivity solutions [11]. As Norway continues to embrace innovation across various sectors, there is an opportunity for the forestry industry to enhance its resilience and sustainability by embracing digital transformation and staying abreast of technological advancements.

The COMTECT project has identified two specific use case applications where 5G private networks can be potentially deployed, as illustrated in Figure 1 (a).

1) *Remote operational support from expert for forest machine operators:* The forestry industry encounters a pressing need for remote expert assistance in thinning and logging activities, where on-site operators require immediate guidance and support. This necessity faces challenges due to the insufficient performance of public MNO networks in forested areas. To address this issue, the proposed solution involves deploying a local 5G private Network on Wheels (NoW), specifically designed for forestry environments, as also shown in Figure 1(a). The 5G private NoW facilitates high-quality video transmissions from forest machinery to enable seamless remote support through online cameras. Experts from the forest operator's company could remotely advise and assist on-site operators in decision-making. Furthermore, the same solution addresses maintenance, detection, and repair of engine or machine errors, with a vendor's expert supervising operators through online cameras utilizing high-quality video feeds at the vendor's location.

2) *Complex situational awareness services in the forest:* The escalating threat of forest fires, exacerbated by global warming, emphasizes the urgent requirement for an advanced monitoring and surveillance system in forested areas. Forests

are susceptible to various emergencies, from wildfires and landslides to floods, necessitating a sophisticated solution to enhance safety for both the natural environment and emergency personnel, including police, ambulance services, fire departments, and volunteers. The existing landscape requires immediate reporting of incidents, such as fires, through digital channels. In response to these challenges, the NoW solution illustrated in Figure 1(a) combined with drone technology alongside on-ground sensors enables a sophisticated monitoring and surveillance environment and promptly notifies emergency personnel in the event of critical incidents. The advanced cameras mounted on drones capture high-resolution, multi-spectral aerial images. These images are streamed in real-time via the private 5G NoW to an external edge server. The integration of on-map analytics further enhances the ability to visualize forest metrics, ensuring an immediate and effective response to alarming changes.

B. Livestock Transportation Use Case

For over a thousand years, the pig industry has been one of the major sources of income in Denmark. The European Union (EU), as well as the Danish authorities, have established a series of regulations that should be followed to ensure the animals' welfare before, during and after transport [12], [13]. After discussions with the stakeholders in the livestock transportation domain, the COMTECT project has identified possible digital solutions that could be beneficial.

One digital solution example is automatic animal counting, which allows efficient and correct counting of livestock, e.g. pigs, when they get on and off the transportation truck. Moreover, the application of a computer vision-based solution would allow the detection of animals' status, e.g. injuries or illness, and evaluate their departure and arrival conditions to ensure that their health status remained unchanged during transport. This would require the transfer of a live video stream of the loading and unloading process with sufficient video quality, which is challenging due to the insufficient uplink performance of public networks in rural areas.

For such a use case, it is essential to realize local wireless network coverage at remote locations. The proposed connec-

Fig. 2. Network on Wheels.

Fig. 3. Measuring points in a dense forest with high vegetation.

tivity solution for the local wireless network is a 5G private network, as shown in Figure 1(b). Depending on the local situation, the farm can either have terrestrial or satellite Internet access to convey the video stream to the remote location, as shown in Figure 1(b). Furthermore, video monitoring might require timely analysis and decisions such that the automated decision loop could be performed in less than a second. Thus, from connectivity point of view, the video analysis should be done ‘in the edge’, i.e. nearby to the farm locations.

IV. NETWORK DESIGN, DEPLOYMENT AND PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

This section presents, for both the forestry and the livestock transportation use cases, the network designs and deployments used for the evaluations. Moreover, the performance achieved with the deployed 5G private networks, are presented in term of throughput.

A. 5G NPN in Forestry Use Cases

The COMMECT forestry use cases rely on high uplink throughput for transmission of high-quality videos from remote forestry machinery as well as from flying drones. In order to satisfy this high uplink throughput demand, the NoW concept of a 5G private network is introduced. NoW serves as a self-contained entity, encompassing 5G radio, 5G core, and ancillary applications within a singular, effortlessly transportable mobile framework as shown in Figure 2. It provides a complete standalone 5G private network that can be set up quickly and provides 5G coverage. The NoW traffic is back-hauled either via terrestrial networks or via satellite, depending on the need and location, for reach back purposes to the cloud or the Internet for remote expert opinion. To provide real-time forest monitoring and surveillance for situational awareness, the NoW’s Edge server can be equipped with AI/ML algorithms for efficient detection of any unwanted incidents like forest fires or any other anomalies. Furthermore, the equipment in NoW is powered by an ecoflow battery unit that provides a battery backup of around 2 hours, depending upon the load. The batteries can be charged on the field with an external gasoline generator.

The NoW set-up in Figure 2 also supports Public Protection and Disaster Relief (PPDR) use cases by utilizing the PPDR frequency spectrum in a range between 3300-3400 MHz as well as the 5G private frequency spectrum (3800-4200 MHz) in Norway. In an effort to leverage NoW technology for forestry applications, we conducted an initial assessment of its coverage and connectivity performance. The NoW was placed in a selected location in the forest, and then uplink throughput measurements were performed with a smartphone for locations deep in the very dense forest. The tests were performed using 80 MHz of bandwidth in the 3300-3400 MHz frequency band. The transmit power was set to 35 dBm with antenna height of 2.5 m. We set up an uplink-loaded frame structure uplink/downlink (3:7) that benefits the high uplink. The measuring points in the forest are shown in Figure 3. Due to the thick forest, it was difficult to take measurements further away from the NoW location. The measurements were taken on the Huawei p40 smartphone at a natural holding height of 1.5 m. We used the web-based OpenSpeedTest tool¹, deployed on the edge server in NoW, which measures internet speed, including upload, download, and latency, directly through a browser without the need for additional software. The test utilizes multiple TCP streams to evaluate download and upload speeds. The speed test server can be accessible via phones/CPEs connected to the 5G network. Moreover, the distance between the base station and the measurement point is evaluated using the Global Positioning System (GPS) coordinates of the base station and the measurement point, resulting in an accuracy of around 10 feet. Furthermore, no backhauling was used as we were interested in the performance of the 5G private network.

Figure 4 shows the average uplink throughput against the measurement points inside the forest. With the current configuration, we are able to achieve an average uplink throughput of around 10 Mbps, even at a distance of around 300 m deep in the forest. These high uplink values are sufficient to support both of the COMMECT forestry use cases. Moreover, the coverage distance can be further increased by increasing the transmit antenna height, the height of the receiving unit with

¹<https://openspeedtest.com/selfhosted-speedtest>

Fig. 4. Average uplink throughput measured at the forest.

multiple antennas and other features like beamforming.

B. 5G NPN in Livestock Transportation Use Case

For COMTECT’s livestock loading and unloading video monitoring application, a high-definition uplink real-time video streaming is expected with a throughput of 10 Mbps in the uplink wireless access link [14]. Considering that farm locations usually lack connectivity, it is proposed that a local 5G private network is deployed, which is complemented with either terrestrial or satellite networks. In this paper, we are focused on the performance of the local 5G private network and, more specifically, of an SNPN.

To address the performance of the SNPN, field tests have been performed at a selected farm location in the Netherlands. For the tests, the Amarisoft CallBox Classic² has been used to act as an SNPN, as shown in Figure 5(a), and it was configured to use spectrum from 3,825 MHz to 3,875 MHz in the n77 band (3.3 GHz to 4.2 GHz). Moreover, two different bandwidth sizes, i.e. 20 MHz and 50 MHz, and a more ‘uplink friendly’ TDD frame configuration, i.e. three uplink frames and seven downlink frames, have been considered. The maximum transmission power used during the field tests was -20 dBm/MHz, which results in a transmission power of -7 dBm for 20 MHz and -3 dBm for 50 MHz. The tests aim to quantify the size of the covered area around the installed private 5G base station (in this scenario, provided by the Amarisoft CallBox) where the required uplink throughput of 10 Mbps can be achieved. Therefore, uplink transmissions were performed from the Quectel RM502Q-GL towards the Amarisoft CallBox at different locations at the farm, as shown in Figure 5(b). The maximum achievable uplink throughput was measured using iPerf3³ in User Datagram Protocol (UDP) mode to simulate the transmission of a video stream, as UDP is commonly used by video streaming codecs due to its latency characteristics and tolerance for packet loss.

²<https://www.amarisoft.com/test-and-measurement/device-testing/device-products/amari-callbox-classic>

³<https://iperf.fr/>

Figure 6 shows the obtained uplink throughput, averaged over multiple measurements per location, and illustrates that a higher bandwidth leads to a higher achieved uplink throughput and, thus, satisfactory uplink coverage, as expected. Specifically, the 10 Mbps target can be reached for up to roughly 40 m and 55 m, with 20 MHz and 50 MHz, respectively. Note that the mentioned values provide a rough indication of uplink throughput versus coverage performance as this depends on the network node’s configuration (e.g. bandwidth, transmit power, number of receiver antennas, terminal uplink capabilities, etc.), as well as radio channel and interference conditions.

C. Summary

Two different deployment scenarios (with the NoW and with the Amarisoft CallBox) have been investigated for the two use cases, which generate different results in terms of achievable uplink throughput over distance. This performance difference stems from a combination of different effects. Firstly, a higher bandwidth has been considered in the NoW deployment, which naturally leads to higher throughput. Additionally, the NoW uses an active antenna unit with 32x32 TxRx antenna elements capable of beamforming, whereas the Amarisoft CallBox uses omnidirectional antennas. Thus, a higher receiver gain can be obtained with the NoW, which in return provides higher uplink throughput. Moreover, the transmit power with the NoW is significantly higher than with the Amarisoft CallBox, which further influences the throughput versus distance performance. Specifically, the antenna in combination with the transmit power at the base station have an impact on the pilot measurements at the device, which are then used to configure the transmit power and the modulation and coding scheme of the device for the uplink transmission. Taking these deployment differences into account, it is highlighted that the performance of the 5G private network, in terms of throughput, heavily depends on the RAN configuration, e.g. bandwidth, transmission powers and antenna arrays, and that higher investment in high-quality and high-performance equipment can significantly improve the network performance.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The 5G private network solutions proposed by COMTECT address the challenges of MNOs in rural areas, where sparse population density generates unprofitable investment and high capital and operational expenditures. Two main use cases have been identified, one related to forest monitoring and another to livestock transportation. For both use cases, connectivity solutions have been proposed to address the respective use case requirements, and initial insights on the performance of each connectivity solution have been provided.

For future work, more tests and trials will be performed. For the forest use case, tests and trials will be conducted using various frequency bands, including n40 and n79, for coverage evaluation and channel modelling. Moreover, Internet connectivity will be evaluated, considering both low earth orbit satellites and mobile networks. For the livestock transportation use case, a similar set of measurements will be performed

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. (a) Measurement setup with Amarisoft CallBox Classic and (b) measurement locations at the farm.

Fig. 6. Average uplink throughput measured at the farm location.

using a Wi-Fi router to compare the performance of 5G private networks to Wi-Fi networks utilising unlicensed spectrum. Also, the applicability of satellite links will be investigated with field tests by connecting, e.g., the Amarisoft SNPN to the Internet and measuring the end-to-end delay performance for the real-time video stream towards the remote location.

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